

**TO THE QUESTION OF CREATING OPTIMAL TRANSLATION
EXERCISES AND THEIR APPLICATION IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING A
FOREIGN LANGUAGE**

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Annotation: A new format of exercises for mastering translation skills is considered; the main formats for using tasks are analyzed, which allow using them as a simulator in the teaching process.

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As you know, there are different opinions in the methodology in relation to translation exercises. Some methodologists believe that such exercises do not contribute to the fluency of a foreign language and therefore recommend not to include them in the system of exercises. The disadvantages of translation are usually attributed to the fact that it:

- a) immediately presents a complex of difficulties, disperses attention;
- b) takes a lot of time.

With the constant use of translation, the teacher deliberately takes a detour, constantly evoking the mental complexes of the native language, which does not at all contribute to the formation of a foreign language dynamic stereotype. Self-development of skills involves self-compilation of an expression plan, determination of its content, selection of words, etc. When translating, all this is someone else's, ready-made. Translation is completely devoid of situationality. However, translation can find its place in teaching writing. Many Western European methodologists and authors of books on foreign languages have a similar opinion.

Educational translation should be considered as one of the means of teaching a foreign language. Its benefit or harm is determined not by the nature of translation as such,

but by how it is applied in the educational process. If educational translation is used as the main means of teaching a foreign language, then this is harmful and cannot bring any positive results.

Translation can serve both as a means of explaining the language material and as a means of consolidating it, as well as a means of its control .

Among the grammar exercises, there is a translation of phrases containing difficult grammatical phenomena. In certain situations, we cannot do without translation. These situations, from his point of view, are as follows:

- when mastering language material during the period of semantization of lexical units and lexico-grammatical phenomena. In such cases, translation is the most economical and most accurate way of semantization;
- in the course of performing special exercises aimed at testing language knowledge and skills;
- when teaching informative reading in order to check the depth
- witness. In these cases, selective translation of fragments of the studied text is most often used;
- When a specialist needs to determine the information encoded in the text with maximum accuracy.

Translation can have a positive impact on foreign language learning in the following cases:

- when semantizing lexical units,
- when defining and explaining grammatical material,
- when checking what was understood after listening,
- when checking the text understood after reading,
- when learning to translate someone else's speech,
- when teaching some statements, constructions, phrases that are not formed according to the rules and difficult to access paragraphs,
- when learning to translate from one's native language into a foreign language , and from a foreign language into one's native language.

The reason for the negative attitude towards translation exercises, in our opinion, is the deep disappointment of teachers and methodologists in the grammar-translation method, in which translation from a foreign language into a native language was considered the only means of teaching a foreign language in the first half of the 20th century and the emergence of a direct method as an alternative to this. method. The direct method, as you know, required direct teaching of a foreign language, i.e. teaching a foreign language without involving the native language. From our point of view, those methodologists are right who avoid these two opposite opinions about the role of translation exercises. They, as we noted above, believe that translation exercises are needed in certain circumstances.

Translation exercises are indeed one of the necessary means of teaching a foreign language. The usefulness of such exercises is explained by the fact that at the initial stage of learning a foreign language (with subordinate bilingualism), a person thinks in his native language, that is, he generates a statement in his native language in his mind (this is called inner speech), then translates this internal statement into a foreign language . In other words, internal speech in the native language turns into external speech in a foreign language.

into a foreign language still takes place in subordinative bilingualism . Everyone who has studied a foreign language after mastering their native language knows this. To ensure a quick and correct transition from the native language to a foreign language, it is necessary, along with other types of exercises, to apply translation exercises.

In order for translation exercises to take their rightful place among other exercises, they should be improved. In our opinion, this can be done in the following way.

First, the teacher should create a system of diaforms, if one is not already made. Diaforms are speech samples of a foreign language, provided with their adequate translations - speech samples of the native language. Vocabulary should be familiar in speech samples. Students must memorize diaforms i.e. memorize speech samples with their translations. At the same time, more attention should be paid to the translation of speech samples of the native language into speech samples of a foreign language, because

it is easier to understand foreign speech than to speak it. Diaforms are memorized at home. They form translation stereotypes in the student, which prevent interlingual interference.

We propose to divide translation exercises into pre-speech translation exercises and speech (communicative) translation exercises. Pre-speech translation exercises are compiled on the basis of the compiled diaforms. Their students can perform not only in the classroom, but also at home. In this case, students have enough time to translate each sentence. Pre-speech translation exercises may contain unfamiliar vocabulary and students can use a dictionary.

Speech (communicative) translation exercises proposed by us are based on instant spontaneous oral translation. With instant translation, the student has the text in his hand and, looking at it, but not reading it aloud, translates it instantly. In other words, with instant translation into a foreign language, the student translates sentences (utterances) immediately after their presentation. Such translation approaches simultaneous translation, but it does not become simultaneous. Memorizing diaforms as a kind of pre-speech exercises should precede the performance of speech (communicative) translation exercises.

So, our proposed methodology for performing translation exercises consists of three stages:

1. Learning diaforms by heart in extracurricular time;
2. Performing pre-speech translation exercises in extracurricular or classroom time;
3. Performing speech (communicative) translation exercises in class time.

Diaform proficiency is checked in pair work using the list of diaforms that each partner has in pair work. First, the first partner checks the second partner, and then the second partner checks the first. At the same time, the verified partner should not have a list of diaforms with him. Then both partners will report to the teacher about the results of the test. We also recommend holding an educational competition on the strength of assimilation of diaforms in paired groups, minigroups and in the whole group.

Educational competition is an important incentive to increase students' interest in winning. It also increases the responsibility of each participant in the competition to his team, so as not to let his team down.

Literature:

1. Passov E.I. Fundamentals of foreign language teaching methodology. M.: Russian language, 2017.
2. Demyanenko M.Ya. et al. Fundamentals of the general methodology of teaching foreign languages. Kyiv: Higher School, 2016.
3. Rakhmanov I.V. Teaching oral speech in a foreign language. Moscow: Higher school, 2018.